
What is the polarizability of element 119?

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Abstract In the present work, an extrapolation approach is employed to calculate the polarizability (10^{-24}cm^3) for element 119, from the absolute hardness for the cation 119^+ . The calculated value: 67.49, is in total disagreement with the value calculated by using sophisticated relativistic quantum chemical approach [7], 25.12 (or 169.7, in atomic units). It is considered here that the relativistic effects, for element 119 (of course, regarding polarizability), in such calculations [7-9], have been overestimated, and that the value obtained by extrapolation is the reliable one. The proposed explanation for such difference is based on Clementi effective nuclear charge values: since Cs, with $Z_{\text{eff}} = 6.36$, has a polarizability of 59.42, seems quite natural that element 119, with $Z_{\text{eff}} = 6.20$, will have a larger polarizability, since we have almost the same effective nuclear charge (Cs and element 119), but in element 119 the “electron cloud” has 64 more electrons (119-55).

Keywords Polarizability, superheavy elements, element 119, absolute hardness, effective nuclear charge

Introduction

Taking into account that, for superheavy elements, direct measurements of their chemical and physical properties are difficult or even impossible tasks, a lot of efforts have been made in order to estimate/calculate the properties of such elements, such as their formation enthalpies [1].

In the present work, the polarizability for element 119 is calculated by an empirical equation, employing the absolute hardness for the cation 119^+ . The obtained value is in total disagreement with the values provided by relativistic quantum chemical calculations, and an explanation for such discrepancy is proposed.

Methodology, Results and Discussion

Using the ionization energy values [2,3], absolute hardness values (eV) for Li^+ (35.12), Na^+ (21.08), K^+ (13.64), Rb^+ (11.56) and Cs^+ (9.61) were calculated. Such values are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Absolute hardness and polarizabilities for group 1 cations/elements

Specie/property	η^+ /eV	polarizability/ 10^{-24}cm^3
Li		24.33
Li^+	35.12	
Na		24.11
Na^+	21.08	
K		43.06
K^+	13.64	
Rb		47.24
Rb^+	11.56	

Cs	59.42
Cs ⁺	9.61

When the (static dipole) polarizabilities (10^{-24} cm^3) for group 1 atoms (from Li to Cs) [4] are plotted as function of the absolute hardness for the respective cations (Table 1), the curve shown in Figure 1 is obtained, from which the following equation is derived:

$$P = -6.223 + 214.637 \exp(-\eta^+/5.473) + 28.711 \exp(-\eta^+/(7.546 \times 10^{86})) \quad (1)$$

As a consistency test, Eq. (1) was applied to francium. However, before this, was necessary to calculate η^+ for francium.

Figure 1: Polarizabilities as a function of monocation absolute hardness for group 1 elements (from Li to Cs)

In order to calculate the absolute hardness for the monocation, we need to know the first and second ionization energies for the neutral atom. In the literature [2,3] only the first ionization energy for francium is available. Hence, the second ionization energy was estimated as follows: the second ionization energies for Na, K, Rb and Cs, were plotted as function of the respective first ionization energies, proving the curve shown in Figure 2 ($r = 0.9979$), from which the following equation was derived:

$$IE_2 = 19.671IE_1 - 19.671 \quad (2)$$

Where E_1 and E_2 are the first and second ionization energies, respectively. Applying, in Eq. (2) the E_1 value for Fr = 4.07 eV [2,3], the second ionization energy can be calculated as 26.10 eV and then, the absolute hardness for Fr⁺ can be calculated as 11.02 eV

Applying this value in Eq. (1), the polarizability (10^{-24} cm^3) for francium is calculated as 51.14, in very good agreement with the reference value [3]: 48.60.

The decrease in the polarizability values from Cs to Fr is in agreement with a relativistic contraction [5]. Hence, from Fr to element 119, one can expect also a decrease in polarizability.

Figure 2: Second ionization energies as a function of the first ionization energies for group 1 elements (from Na to Cs).

The absolute hardness for 119^+ can be calculated as 8.55 eV, using the mean values calculated to the first and second ionization energies for element 119: 3.69-3.80 eV [6] and 20.3-21.4 eV [6], respectively. Applying this value in Eq.(1), a polarizability of 67.49 is calculated to element 119.

Such result is a really unexpected one by two reason:

- Due to the relativistic contraction [5], one can expect that the polarizability for element 119 will be lower than that for Fr (such as the polarizability for Fr is lower than that for Cs);
- Furthermore, and in agreement with the previous statement, using sophisticated relativistic quantum chemical approach, the polarizability (10^{-24} cm^3) for element 119 was calculated as 25.12 (or 169.7, in atomic units) [7] and such calculated value is in very good agreement with another ones [8,9], also obtained by relativistic quantum chemical calculations.

In a first moment, one can tend to believe that, obviously, the value calculated by using sophisticated relativistic quantum chemical procedures are the reliable ones, and look for the mistake that was done.

Plotting the polarizabilities as function of the absolute hardness, from Na to Fr, or from Rb to Fr, or only to Cs and Fr, linear equations (with $r \approx 0.98$) are obtained, providing calculated polarizability values for element 119 closer to that calculated by using Eq. (1). Hence, apparently, the extrapolation approach seems not be the problem.

As is well known, despite its simplicity (or, maybe, because it) since the times of Mendeleev that extrapolations/interpolations have been successfully employed to estimate/calculate/predict the properties for (even not discovered) elements.

Hence, I will be dare here, and say that my extrapolated value is right and that the relativistic values are wrong. Coherently, is necessary to find an explanation for such discrepancies.

Plotting the Clementi effective nuclear charges [10,11] as a function of the (first) ionization energies (IE) values for groups 1 elements [2,3], (from Li to Cs) the following equation ($r = 0.9545$) is derived:

$$Z_{\text{eff}} = -2.964 IE + 17.318 \quad (3)$$

Using Eq. (3) and the first ionization energies for Fr=4.07 eV [2,3] and element 119= 3.75 eV (the mean value of the previously calculated interval 3.69-3.80 eV [6]) their Clementi effective nuclear charges are calculated as: Fr (5.25) and 119 (6.20).

In order to verify the reliability of the calculated Z_{eff} values, the following approach was employed: the polarizabilities for group 1 elements (from Li to Cs) were plotted as a function of the Clementi Z_{eff} , and the curve shown in Figure 3 was obtained ($r = 0.9568$), from which the following equation was derived:

$$P = 7.314 Z_{\text{eff}} + 12.381 \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Polarizabilities as a function of nuclear effective charges for group 1 elements (from Li to Cs)

Applying the previously calculated Z_{eff} value for francium (5.25) in Eq. (4), a polarizability of 50.78 is calculated, in very good agreement with the reference value [3]: 48.60. Applying the same equation to element 119, a polarizability of 57.73 is calculated, in not so good agreement with the 67.49 value calculated using Eq. (1) but, anyway, in much better agreement than the 25.12 [7] value calculated by relativistic quantum chemical methods.

It is worth noting that simply dividing the non-relativistic value for element 119 polarizability (685.5 au) [12] by $\gamma = 1/[1 - ((Z/137)^2/c^2)]^{1/2}$ (a relativistic parameter; Z = the atomic number, c = speed of light) = 2.02, we obtain 339.4 au = 50.2 (10^{-24} cm^3), which is in good agreement with the value calculated by using Eq. (4). That is, the relativistic contribution is present, of course, but it has been overestimated [7-9].

Hence, some points must be highlighted here, as conclusions:

- The obtained results shown that the polarizability of element 119 is much higher than the one predicted by relativistic quantum chemical calculations [7-9];
- The relativistic quantum chemical calculations [7-9] provides polarizabilities results for element 119 very different from those obtained by extrapolation, using ionization energies, nuclear effective

- charges or absolute hardness as related parameters. Hence, the relativistic effects, for such element (of course, regarding polarizability), in such calculations, have been overestimated;
- c) Along period 1, the Clementi Z_{eff} [10,11] values increases: Li (1.28), Na (2.51), K (3.50), Rb (4.98) and Cs (6.36). The Z_{eff} decreases for Fr (5.25) and increases again to element 119 (6.20);
 - d) Such phenomena could, in a first moment, be associated with the anti-screening effect proposed/calculated by Ershov [13,14], been supposed that for element 119 such effect/phenomena is prominent.
 - e) Since Cs, with $Z_{\text{eff}} = 6.36$, has a polarizability of 59.42, seems quite natural that element 119, with $Z_{\text{eff}} = 6.20$ will have a larger polarizability (67.49, by using Eq. 1): they have practically the same effective nuclear charge (Cs and element 119), but in element 119 the “electrons cloud” has 64 more electrons (119-55).

The previous argument get stronger if we leave into account that the covalent radius of Cs is 238 pm [3] and for element 119 it can be estimated as 223 pm, by using the Hartree-Fock scalar relativistic bond distance for 119H [15]: the radius variation is so small (15 pm) to justify the variation in polarizabilities (atomic units) from 399 (Cs) to 169.7 (element 119) [7], specially taking into account that in element 119 the “electrons cloud” has 64 more electrons (119-55), whereas element 119 has a minor Z_{eff} than cesium.

Since element 119 is the first one of the eighth period of the periodic table, could be supposed that such “attenuation” of relativistic contributions, will be observed for element 120 and beyond.

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